

ONLINE SHOPPING AND FOLKLORE - A REVIEW: WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INDIA

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research paper is to classify factors affecting the online shopping in India. The weighty growth of online shopping is noticeable in India. More and more consumer is transferring to online shopping rather than traditional buying methods. Many myths and misconceptions emerge in India regarding online shopping. Every new thing, when it is not cleared by all the people properly, it is only a nightmare. Online shopping is intricate in nature. As we know the number of online transactions have been increased, but it is still under the dark room. Government and E-commerce companies should take necessary steps for reducing the level of misconceptions and myths of online shopping in India. This research paper's purpose is to identifying 'How' the companies can be able to overcome these fake information regarding online shopping. Also improve company's sales figure, for the upliftment of company as well as an Indian economy.

Keywords:

Online Shopping, Myths and Misconceptions, Indian Economy

1. INTRODUCTION

Online shopping means as transaction conducted over the internet. When we purchase a good via internet, its called an online shopping. The fast rate of growth in online transactions is also helpful for upliftment of Indian economy level. Hence myths and misconceptions regarding online shopping still prevail, that's why in front of consumer the growth rate of online transactions in India has reduced. Because of lack of knowledge, there is a doubt which prevails in the mind of consumers. By the passage of time myths have been solved automatically. Now people are more aware inherently about the new things or transformations. As we know online transaction is more fruitful and a fast method for shopping, but still there are so many people who think that, it is a time consuming and a long process.

2. OBJECTIVES

Main objectives of this research paper are as follows:-

1. To find out what are the misconceptions and myths of online transactions in India.
2. To find out what obstacles are being faced by online shopping industry, So that the myths regarding online transaction can be removed.

3. To find out the universe of online transactions in India and 'How' it can be enlarged or grown.
4. To find out how online transactions help to improve today's life style?

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The universe used for the review of literature focuses upon the meaning, scope, myths and misconceptions of online transactions in India.

According to **Susan G. Holl**, Beyond the many advantages of online shopping there are also problems which may occur with online shopping, the problems such as late delivery , receiving the wrong item and returning policy of the websites. A popular misconception is that purchasing a product online does not have warrant or guaranty.

According to **Deepali**, states that demand of electronic item increases day by day. Online shopping is increasing as an astounding rate in recent years. Some online shopping portals in India are www.flipkart.com, www.mynta.com, www.ebay.com.

SCOPE: - Research area mainly focuses upon online shopping misconceptions and myths. Research is emphasized upon what difficulties are being faced by online shopping industry in India and how they can be dealt with the best of their sweats. Research paper also gives stress in finding the materialist solution for avoiding the misconceptions regarding online shopping.

SIGNIFICANCE: - Significance of research paper can be divided into two parts. First is for online shopping industry, it helps to understand more deeply that what problems are being faced for doing online transactions in India and this research paper suggest that how an online transactions industry is helpful to overcome these problems. Second for government to analysis those factors which are responsible for revoke of online transactions in India and how these factors can be reduce by making rules and regulations, giving awareness to people for development of online transaction industry as well as growth of nation.

4. POPULAR MISCONCEPTIONS OF ONLINE TRANSACTIONS IN INDIA

As we know online shopping is new in India, the number of online transactions is increasing regularly. Online shopping helps to works easily and smoothly in busy life schedule but some misconceptions regarding online transactions are as follows:-

4.1. NO WARRANTY

Some of the people think that there is no warranty available in regarding online shopping and no company provide guarantee if customer purchases product online. This is famous misconception regarding purchasing of a brand product.

4.2. LATE DELIVERY

People in India believe that online shopping industry always deliver its product after the cutoff date. They become always late. It is only a Halo effect on consumer's mind. But this demerit does not remain same always.

4.3. LONG AND TIME CONSUMING PROCESS

Some of the people assume that shopping over the internet is very time consuming process and it takes so much time to register on E-commerce website and making an online purchase.

4.4. FRAUD

Popular misconception regarding online shopping is all about E-commerce websites that these are frauds. They steal amount and do not give refund back to customers. Many scams and fraudulent websites are available in current E-commerce market.

Fig 1: Popular Misconceptions of Online Transactions

4.5. ONLY ONE METHOD TO BUY PRODUCTS

Many of the people assume that only credit card is option for making payment for online shopping. They think that without having a visa or credit card, they are not able for doing online transactions in India.

4.6. COSTLY

People in India believe that shopping over internet is much more expensive as compare to traditional shopping methods. They think that extra delivery charges on goods can be taken by customer and not a single low price product available on online purchasing.

4.7. STOLEN PRIVATE INFORMATION

Another misconception regarding online shopping is that, people think that online transaction websites steal customer's private information and sale it to other party for their benefits.

4.8. NOT FOR GIFTS

Some of the people think that by online shopping gift can't be transferred to any other person. But it is an illusion only. The fact is that, it is possible to sending gift via online shopping.

4.9. LOW QUALITY

Another misconception is that people think that by online shopping mode they will get only low or false quality products while purchasing a product. Some people believe that only low quality product can be sold out by website and the quality of sold product may be differentiate from the mentioned product available on website and the products that can be physical transferred.

5. SUGGESTION FOR OVERCOMING MISCONCEPTIONS

Many misconceptions and myths are found in India regarding online transactions. For solving that issues E-commerce websites provide awareness to people about online transactions like giving free counseling session, proper customer care support and provide information in regional language. For better revival of problems of consumers, It is being suggested that free demo of online transactions should be shown on E-commerce website. Also free demo of online transaction is also being shown on E-commerce website. Registration process on E-commerce website is easy, simple and quick. Another suggestion from the researcher's point of view is that an online bill should also be generated, if any online transaction takes place.

6. CONCLUSION

Indian government should take necessary steps to revoke these factors like provide alertness for doing campaign and literate more people for English language and provide guidance more people about internet and computer literacy. Some rules and regulations should also be made for enhancing online transactions like providing information also in regional language. At last but not the least, we conclude that since online transaction industry is new in India, because of this, there are so many misconceptions, gaps, hurdles and hindrances are in front of the online industry in India, which can be solved with an increment number of online transactions that can help to grow for online shopping industry as well as the growth of Indian economy.

7. LIMITATIONS

Some limitations were recognized while interpreting the findings. First, these studies only focus upon myths and misconceptions of online transactions in India, while other factors like brand value of company, Specifications of E-Commerce Website, growth factors and so on are ignored. Second, the Indian online transaction market is huge; question remains still for solving myths and misconception for small scale online shopping websites.

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